

US010995244B2

(12) **United States Patent**
Arkles et al.

(10) **Patent No.:** **US 10,995,244 B2**

(45) **Date of Patent:** **May 4, 2021**

(54) **HIGH-SPEED MOISTURE-CURE HYBRID
SILOXANE/SILSESQUIOXANE-URETHANE
AND SILOXANE/SILSESQUIOXANE-EPOXY
SYSTEMS WITH ADHESIVE PROPERTIES**

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(71) Applicant: **Gelest Technologies, Inc.**, Morrisville, PA (US)

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(72) Inventors: **Barry C. Arkles**, Pipersville, PA (US);
Youlin Pan, Langhorne, PA (US)

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(73) Assignee: **GELEST TECHNOLOGIES, INC.**,
Morrisville, PA (US)

(*) Notice: Subject to any disclaimer, the term of this patent is extended or adjusted under 35 U.S.C. 154(b) by 62 days.

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(21) Appl. No.: **16/562,708**

(22) Filed: **Sep. 6, 2019**

(65) **Prior Publication Data**

US 2020/0002583 A1 Jan. 2, 2020

Related U.S. Application Data

(62) Division of application No. 15/807,987, filed on Nov. 9, 2017, now Pat. No. 10,513,637, which is a division of application No. 14/958,177, filed on Dec. 3, 2015, now Pat. No. 9,879,159.

(60) Provisional application No. 62/089,993, filed on Dec. 10, 2014.

(51) **Int. Cl.**

C09J 11/06	(2006.01)
C08G 18/71	(2006.01)
C08G 18/73	(2006.01)
C08G 18/28	(2006.01)
C07F 7/18	(2006.01)
C08L 63/00	(2006.01)
C08G 77/04	(2006.01)

(52) **U.S. Cl.**

CPC **C09J 11/06** (2013.01); **C07F 7/1804** (2013.01); **C08G 18/289** (2013.01); **C08G 18/718** (2013.01); **C08G 18/73** (2013.01); **C08G 77/04** (2013.01); **C08L 63/00** (2013.01)

(58) **Field of Classification Search**

None
See application file for complete search history.

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Primary Examiner — Clinton A Brooks

(74) *Attorney, Agent, or Firm* — Panitch Schwarze
Belisario & Nadel LLP

(57) **ABSTRACT**

Materials containing the reaction products of a cyclic azasilane with water and a compound or polymer containing an isocyanate or epoxy functional group and methods for their synthesis are provided. Stable mixtures containing a cyclic azasilane and a compound or polymer containing an isocyanate or epoxy functional group according to invention are stored under anhydrous conditions. The invention also provides a novel class of materials, mono and bis(cycloaza) disiloxanes comprising one or two cyclic structures bridged by an Si—O—Si bond.

4 Claims, No Drawings

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Bisphenol A derived epoxies, such as those shown below, can be reacted similarly, but require additional cyclic azasilane to react with hydroxyl groups.

Similarly, N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilacyclopentane can be mixed with 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane under dry conditions without reaction. However, upon exposure to moisture under ambient conditions of 5-85% R H, the mixture rapidly becomes viscous and then transforms to a translucent solid within a few hours.

It is also within the scope of the invention to form gels without formal crosslinking, as shown in the following exemplary reaction.

While a wide variety of epoxy and isocyanate compounds and polymers may be used, it is preferred if the compound or polymer contains at least two reactive groups.

A variety of cyclic azasilanes may be used in the invention, including without limitation the following compounds:

It is also within the scope of the invention to utilize the novel cyclic azasilane, (N,N-dimethylaminopropyl)-aza-2-methyl-2-methoxysilacyclopentane, which is also encompassed by the invention, and which has the following structure:

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The synthesis of analogous compounds are described in U.S. Patent Application Publication No. 2004/0077892 of Applicants, which is herein incorporated by reference. Briefly, 3-(N,N-dimethylaminopropylamino)propylmethyl-
 10 dimethoxysilane is heated with 2 mole % ammonium sulfate. Methanol is removed slowly under low vacuum conditions, giving an equilibrium mixture of cyclic and oligomeric species. When the formation of methanol approaches stoichiometry, vacuum is increased and the cyclic azasilane is
 15 distilled from the equilibrating mixture.

It is also within the scope of the invention to utilize bis(cycloaza)disiloxanes, such as bis(n-butyl-1-methoxycycloaza-1-silacyclopentyl)ether:
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Mono and bis(cycloaza)silanes are a novel class of compound which are also encompassed by the present invention. These compounds comprise one or two cyclic structures
 30 bridged by an Si—O—Si bond. Other specific examples of these compounds which are included in the invention include N-alkylaminoalkylcyclo-disiloxanes, in which there is one cyclic structure bridged to another silicon atom by an
 35 Si—O—Si bond, and N-butyl-1-methoxy-1-(n-butylaminopropyl)dimethoxysiloxycycloazasilane. That is, a disiloxane structure in which only one of the cyclic rings is formed also has utility as a curing agent. For bis(n-butyl-1-methoxycycloaza)disiloxane, the single cyclic ring structure is n-butyl-
 40 1-methoxy-1-(n-butylaminopropyl)dimethoxysiloxycycloazasilane.

Since bis(cycloaza)silanes do not rely on the relatively slow hydrolysis of alkoxy groups bound to silicon, compared to the high-speed hydrolysis of the Si—N bond, the rate of cure is accelerated. In a sense, the Si—O—Si bond is
 45 formed in advance of the primary ring-opening reaction rather than after it.

In addition to the materials, stable mixtures, and compounds described previously, the invention also relates to methods for forming the materials described above. Specifically, a method for forming a hybrid siloxane/silsesquioxane-urethane or hybrid siloxane/silsesquioxane-epoxy material with adhesive properties involves first reacting a
 50 cyclic azasilane with a compound or polymer containing an isocyanate or epoxy functional group under low moisture conditions, to form a reaction mixture. While any water

8

molecules will consume azasilane and initiate the product formation, it may be understood that the exposure of water cannot be so great so as to increase the viscosity of the reaction mixture such that it is not pourable. Optionally, the reaction mixture further comprises a catalyst or accelerator, such as dibutyl-dilauryl-tin, dimethyl-tindineodecanote, or titanium diisopropoxide bis(pentanedionate). The reaction mixture may be stored under anhydrous conditions for six months or even longer. Subsequently, the reaction mixture is exposed to moisture (preferably 50-85% relative humidity) to form the desired hybrid material.
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The invention may be understood in conjunction with the following, non-limiting examples.

EXAMPLE 1

Reaction of
 N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilylcyclopentane with
 3-Isocyanatopropyltrimethoxysilane
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A 25 ml three neck flask equipped with magnetic stirrer, pot thermometer, rubber septum, and an adapter connected to a N₂ bubbler was charged with 1.0 g (5 mmol) of N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilylcyclopentane. 1.0 g (5 mmol) of 3-isocyanatopropyltrimethoxysilane was added in about 5 min. No exotherm was observed and the mixture remained liquid. After being stirred at room temperature for 15 min, two drops of water were added, the pot temperature rose 6° C., and a very viscous liquid formed. One drop of the mixture was placed on a glass slide and a pale yellow film formed in about two hours.
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EXAMPLE 2

Reaction of
 N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilacyclopentane with
 1,3Bis(glycidoxypropyl)tetramethyldisiloxane
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A 250 ml three neck flask equipped with magnetic stirrer, pot thermometer, rubber septum, and an adapter connected to a N₂ bubbler was charged with 40.7 g (0.2 mol) of N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilylcyclopentane. 36.3 g (0.1 mol) of 1,3-bis(glycidoxypropyl)tetramethyldisiloxane were added over 15 min. No exotherm was observed and the mixture remained liquid. After being stirred at room temperature for 2 hours, 3.6 g (0.2 mol) of water were added, the pot temperature rose from 20 to 31° C. over 10 min, and a very viscous liquid formed. After being stirred at room temperature for 3 hours, the pot temperature rose another 6° C. over 10 min and a gel-like material formed.

EXAMPLE 3

Reaction of
N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilacyclopentane with
1,6-Diisocyanatohexane

A 25 ml three neck flask equipped with magnetic stirrer, pot thermometer, rubber septum, and an adapter connected to a N₂ bubbler was charged with 1.0 g (5 mmol) of N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilylcyclopentane. 0.4 g (2.5 mmol) of 1,6-diisocyanatohexane was added. No exotherm was observed and the mixture remained a liquid. After being stirred at room temperature for 15 min, two drops of water were added, the pot temperature rose 7° C., and a very viscous liquid formed. One drop of the mixture was placed on a glass slide and pale yellow solids formed in about two hours.

EXAMPLE 4

Reaction of
N-n-butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilacyclopentane with
Bisphenol A

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A 250 ml three neck flask equipped with magnetic stirrer, pot thermometer, rubber septum, and an adapter connected to a N_2 bubbler was charged with 20.3 g (0.1 mol) of N-n-butyl-aza-silacyclopentane. 22.8 g (0.05 mol) of bisphenol-A propoxyate diglycidyl ether were added over 15 min. A very mild exotherm was observed (about 3° C.) and the mixture remained liquid. After being stirred at room temperature for four hours, 0.8 g of water was added. The pot temperature rose from 20 to 27° C. over 10 min and a very viscous liquid formed. After being stirred at room temperature for 1 hour, 1.0 g of water was added, the pot temperature rose from 20 to 25° C. over 10 min, and a solid mass formed.

EXAMPLE 5

Formation of
n-Butyl-aza-2,2-dimethoxysilacyclopentane

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A 2000 ml three neck flask equipped with magnetic stirrer, pot thermometer, and four foot long packing column with a distillation head was charged with 588.5 g (2.5 mol) of n-butylamino-propyltrimethoxysilane and 2.5 g of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$. The pot mixture was heated at 160 to 180° C. with ~50 mmHg over 20 to 40 hours. Methanol was removed from the pot at its formation and crude product mixture was collected in a receiver. Redistillation of the crude afforded the pure title compound: 339 g (53%). FTIR and GC-MS confirmed the structure of products. MS: m/z (%): 203 (M+, 7), 160(M+-C3H7, 100).

EXAMPLE 6

Formation of n-Butyl-1-methoxy-1-(n-butylamino-propyl)dimethoxysiloxycycloazasilane and Bis(n-butyl-1-methoxycycloaza-1-silacyclopentyl)ether

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A 2000 ml three neck flask equipped with magnetic stirrer, pot thermometer, and a one foot long packed column mounted with a distillation head was charged with 637.1 g (1.5 mol) of 1,3-di(n-butylamino)propyl-1,1,3,3-tetraethoxydisiloxane and 3.2 g of (NH₄)₂SO₄. The pot mixture was heated at 160 to 180° C. at -2 to 5 mmHg over 20 to 40 hours. Methanol was removed from the pot at its formation. The resulted pot crude was then distilled with 0.3 mmHg at a pot temperature below 180° C. to afford 179 g (37%) of a mixture of monocyclic and bicyclic compounds: FTIR and GC-MS confirmed the structure of products. MS of the monocyclic: m/z (%), 392 (M+, 1%), 360(M+-MeOH), 317(M+-MeOH-C₃H₇, 100%). MS of the bicyclic: m/z (%), 360(M+, 5%), 317(M+-C₃H₇, 100%).

It will be appreciated by those skilled in the art that changes could be made to the embodiments described above without departing from the broad inventive concept thereof. It is understood, therefore, that this invention is not limited to the particular embodiments disclosed, but it is intended to cover modifications within the spirit and scope of the present invention as defined by the appended claims.

We claim:

1. A material comprising a reaction product of a cyclic azasilane with water and a compound or polymer comprising an isocyanate functional group, wherein the cyclic azasilane is selected from azasilanes having the following structures:

14

2. A material comprising a reaction product of a cyclic azasilane with water and a compound or polymer comprising an epoxy functional group, wherein the cyclic azasilane is selected from azasilanes having the following structures:

3. A compound bis(n-butyl-1-methoxycycloaza-1-silacyclopentyl)ether.

4. A compound N-butyl-1-methoxy-1-(n-butylaminopropyl)dimethoxysiloxycycloazasilane.

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